
Ensuring Competitiveness of Business Entities' Products with Market Demand and Increasing Competition

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Abstract: Entrepreneurship is the largest sector of the economy of our country, and the stable and modern development of this sector determines employment and welfare of the population, saturation of markets with quality goods and services, formation of fair prices. level and pace of development of the country's economy. There are a number of factors that determine the effective activity of enterprises, and the role of competition in these factors is of particular importance. Effective organization of competitive activity provides enterprises in the competitive struggle, creates conditions for successful work in the market. Therefore, today it is important to study such problems as the lack of competition in the activities of small enterprises, its features, and to develop certain proposals and recommendations for effective organization. This article attempts to highlight some aspects of the manifestation of competition and its features in the activities of small enterprises.

Key words: enterprise, competition, compete, market, market segment, low costs, competitive strategy, competitive advantage, ways to compete.

Introduction.

Today, our state pays great attention to the development of the business sector. The fact that the share of the industry in the GDP of the country is 55% shows the economic competence of the industry and the importance of its development. In such conditions, it is an important task for scientific research to study the activities of enterprises and to identify the negative situations that hinder their development, to develop measures and recommendations for their elimination. Since businesses usually operate in competitive markets, they always operate in highly competitive markets.

Representatives of the business sector that can withstand strong competition will have the right to continue their activities in the network, naturally, a number of firms will not be able to withstand such strong competition and will be forced to stop their activities. According to the statistics agency of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the number of business entities operating in the Republic of Uzbekistan as of July 1, 2024 was 390,898, and the number of small business entities that ceased to operate in the same year was more than 43,049. As it is clear from this situation, the fact that a significant part of the established business entities are ceasing their activity shows that there are a number of problems that need to be solved in the organization of economic activity in enterprises.

Literature review.

Taking into account the role and importance of enterprises in the economy, it is not difficult to understand the importance of the development of the sector for the country's economy. Enterprises operate under conditions of intense competition in competitive markets, and their economic activity and efficiency directly depend on the ability to compete in these enterprises.

Therefore, this topical issue has always been in the attention of scientists. A number of researches have been carried out by the leading scientists of the world within the framework of the specific

features of competition and its invisibility, and the scientific conclusions produced by these scientists are considered a valuable resource in the organization of competition in enterprises.

"Competition is a key factor that determines whether a company will succeed or fail" (Porter, 2018).

Competition in an industry stems from the fundamentals of the economic structural structure of the industry and goes far beyond the behavior of existing competitors (Porter, 2016).

Produce what the consumer needs and don't try to sell him what you can produce (Fatchutdinov, 1997).

Research methodology.

Methods used in the effective use of competition in the activities of business enterprises: induction and deduction, observation, comparison, factor analysis, synthesis and others.

Analysis and discussion of results.

In the current conditions of globalization, the development of countries and the solution of social and economic problems depend to a large extent on the level of compliance of the products of business entities with the market demand. By its very nature, this sector is very sensitive to changes in our economy.

Today, when our country is entering new stages of its social and economic development, it is very important to ensure that the products of business entities meet the market demand and to increase competition. Unlike the first years of the republic's independence, now business entities are active in all sectors of the economy.

The experience of developed countries shows that ensuring that the products of business entities meet market demand and increasing competition in all spheres of the economy, the wide development of the population has created conditions for a higher standard of living by providing employment, and we are witnessing that it has helped to eliminate economic problems in the country. In addition, in our country, great attention is being paid to the development of this sector, increasing its role and place in the economy, and comprehensive reforms are being carried out in the sector.

The field of ensuring compliance of products of business entities with market demand and increasing competition has a number of advantages. In particular, it is possible to organize enterprises in this field without large costs. At the same time, they quickly adapt to market requirements, quickly change the product production strategy depending on the market situation, have the ability to solve economic problems relatively quickly, and the ability to supply necessary products to domestic and foreign markets increases.

Measures for the development of the area cannot be considered sufficient. The task of studying the latest and most relevant measures used for the development of this sector in developed countries and further strengthening their implementation based on the characteristics of our economy remains urgent.

The development of adaptation of the products of business entities to the market demand expands the possibilities of employment of able-bodied people, in particular, it creates conditions for the creation of new jobs for our young people who have reached adulthood and are eager to work. In particular, there will be opportunities to use unused internal resources and capabilities. production and service processes will be accelerated, inefficient use of resources, looting and corruption will be eliminated, and product production and service provision will be established based on market requirements.

Despite the changes implemented by our country in the field, a number of shortcomings still remain today in terms of supporting entrepreneurship and creating conditions for them. The development of entrepreneurship and the creation of new jobs are not yet at the level of demand.

Lack of knowledge in the field, shortcomings in conducting business, lack of legal literacy, high level of risk in competitive conditions, inability to effectively conduct business in the market, lack of experience in finding partners, etc. The existence of such problems creates the need for a broad approach to the development of the sector.

The decree aimed at strengthening the protection of guarantees of private property and owners' rights in the Republic of Uzbekistan, fundamentally improving the system of organizing support for business initiatives, as well as expanding the access of business entities to financial resources and production infrastructure and the opportunities for business entities to use financial resources and production infrastructure. decisions are taken by our government and their implementation is being ensured.

Under the conditions of globalization, enterprises are working in an increasingly developing business environment. On the one hand, new opportunities are constantly emerging, and on the other hand, constantly growing demands are placing new demands on these enterprises. Such a situation is happening at both the macro-economic and micro-economic levels, and it directly affects all areas. Unfortunately, this situation significantly complicates the processes of effective management and development of many organizations.

As it is necessary to ensure that the products of business entities meet the market demand and to develop competition, it is important to reveal its advantages and disadvantages first.

One of the advantages of entrepreneurship is the close relationship with customers. This allows entrepreneurs to quickly monitor the wishes and opinions of customers, respond to them in time and adapt to them. As a result, customers will be able to choose this company's product compared to other products.

Nowadays, the market is filled with all kinds of products and services. In such a situation, enterprises are focusing on increasing the types and scope of their activities, where they should focus on development through innovation. Only then will this innovation lead to a larger segment or industry.

In a competitive environment, the business sector is required to constantly change and adapt to changing market conditions. In order to find a place in the market, they should act with completely new offers.

Entrepreneurship is the basis of stability and economic development. Therefore, in many countries, the entrepreneurship sector is supported by the state. This is manifested in the form of various benefits, subsidies, grants.

In the development of the economy, entrepreneurship plays an invaluable role in creating jobs and increasing employment, contributing to the stability of the economy due to the important attribute of the market economy and its easy adaptability to changes in economic conditions.

Of course, along with its own advantages, the entrepreneurship sector also has a number of disadvantages, and these are manifested in the high level of risk, dependence on large companies and low leadership skills, and difficulties in raising funds, among others. In particular, the lack of funds is considered one of the biggest problems in enterprises. The reasons for this problem can be given as follows:

the flow of investments - in 90% of cases, investors choose large companies with a leading position in the market;

non-availability of high-volume loans (albeit at a high percentage) - most enterprises are often unable to provide collateral for loans and banks are not interested in lending to them;

the recommendation of equipment leasing with high prices is the invalidation of the opportunity to raise funds for the business sector.

The economic importance of the entrepreneurship sector is significantly increasing due to the deepening of the development of the scientific and technological revolution. Today, the growth of business activity is largely related to the informatization of economy and social life, the achievements in the field of the latest technologies, which allowed to automate a large part of the work in this field. As a result, the need to maintain large management personnel is reduced, and the efficiency of enterprises and, accordingly, the attractiveness of small enterprises increases.

It should be noted that the increase in the number of enterprises of entrepreneurs, in turn, led to the increase of competition between enterprises. Competition, in turn, leads to increased profitability and efficiency. Efficiency gains are reflected in productivity gains, labor cost optimization, the level of technology in use, improved capacity utilization, and increased flexibility of the production system, among other important factors.

The main goal of any business is to get maximum profit with minimum cost. The best way is to ensure that you win the competition. This is the result of timely measures to increase the competitiveness of the manufactured products and the enterprise as a whole. The competitiveness of the enterprise is considered dynamic, depending on these internal and external factors.

Under the conditions of settling and development of different ownership relations, economic entities engaged in various industries and sectors of production, service will have their own development strategy based on the opportunities and conditions created in the country. In this process, business enterprises try to easily adjust their activities to one or another level of market demand.

The successful development of each enterprise, its production of products necessary for the population and other consumers at the most optimal price, the optimal ratio between costs and profits, and the conditions for the enterprise's more active operation in the future determine the conditions. Because the general requirements expressed by the population are the motivating factor. In this case, the growth of general demand creates strong incentives to increase the production of almost all goods, especially consumer goods. The result of such stimulating factors is the reason for the emergence of competitive relations, and this process leads to the occurrence of types of pure economic struggle for the buyer's market among the subjects.

In the market economy, the main factor of the commercial success of the goods is the quality of the consumer value of the goods and its competitiveness. This, in turn, can lead to the economic stability of the enterprise. Therefore, the categories of competitiveness of entrepreneurs' enterprises and economic stability are very complex and interconnected, and competitiveness occurs only when there is economic stability. Economic stability is influenced by many internal and external factors, and they are of decisive importance in the development prospects of business enterprises and create the opportunity to win in the competitive environment.

Competition is the driving force of the market economy. In order to win in the competition, entrepreneurs strive to reduce production costs, improve product quality, and facilitate the sale of goods for the buyer. Otherwise, it is impossible to sell goods and make a big profit. It is worth

noting that monopoly is anti-competitive, because it provides monopolies to the producer and does not leave conditions for mutual competition. Therefore, it is necessary to increase measures aimed at limiting monopoly in the development of the country's economy.

As an economic category, "competition" is a relatively common fundamental term. Competition is a complex concept. Competition emerges both as a way of doing business and as a way of ensuring the competition of one capital with another. In addition, competition appears as a disorderly manager of social production.

Competition can be considered as an element of the market mechanism that ensures the interaction of economic entities in the process of production and sale of products, as well as in the field of capital investment. The form of competition is considered to be the system of norms and rules of organization of social production, which is based on state reforms, market methods of national economy consisting of state and private firms. Based on this, it is appropriate to consider that the nature of competition meets the requirements of the market economy as a means of entrepreneurship development.

Competition between product manufacturers is considered to be a struggle to produce products under favorable conditions and to sell them at a price that brings good profits, and to strengthen their position in the economy as a whole. At the same time, they spend the necessary funds for the purchase of the necessary means of production, raw materials and materials, and the hiring of labor. Competition between product manufacturers is ultimately completed by attracting consumers in the market.

Product competition between business entities determines and determines the social value of goods, in other words, the market value. This value usually corresponds to the value of products produced under average conditions and which make up a large part of the goods of a certain industry. As a result of such competition, entities with a high level of technology and labor productivity will receive additional profits, and on the contrary, technically weak enterprises will lose part of the value of their manufactured goods and suffer losses.

Conclusions and suggestions.

Enterprises ensure the development of the economy with their innovative character.

Employment will increase and poverty will decrease.

Markets are filled with goods and help ensure price norms and their fair level.

Speed in the organization of production helps to accelerate the development of the economy.

The rapid accumulation of resources helps the development of technologies.

There are certain disadvantages of enterprises, which are as follows:

- small size
- lack of capital
- difficulties in finding financial resources
- high sensitivity to changes in market conditions
- instability of activity, inability to influence the external environment
- inefficiency in places with a small population, dependence of activities on the decisions of the leader
- difficulties in finding financial partners, difficulties in concluding long-term stable partnership agreements
- intolerance to competition, lack of opportunity to conduct wide activities in the market.

The economic capabilities of enterprises do not allow them to compete in all areas of activity. They need to determine their superior aspects in the market and strengthen these aspects to fight the competition. Companies compete in a certain segment of the market to provide them with an advantage. The competitive strategies they choose should be aimed at ensuring a competitive advantage based on the effective use of the advantages of certain segments of the market. Regardless of whether companies use an offensive or defensive strategy, they cannot be passive in competition, avoiding competition can have a negative impact on their competitiveness. Therefore, it is important for such enterprises to develop their competitiveness by adapting their activities to market changes.

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